

G-Cubed

Supporting Information for

Fingerprinting kinetic isotope effects and diagenetic exchange reactions using fluid inclusion and dual-clumped isotope analysis.

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Text S1. Supplementary Discussion Regarding the CEF model:

The Carbonate Exchange Fraction Model (CEF Model) was initially constructed to describe fluid inclusions and carbonate clumped isotopes in abiogenic carbonate (Nooitgedacht et al., 2021a). It appears that the new “dual-clumped” isotope data are in agreement with the CEF model as originally proposed, given that the theoretical lines for a mass balance model always intersect measured values in Δ_{47} - Δ_{48} space (Figure 2, main text). This makes sense given the relatively low water/rock ratios used in these experiments. The CEF values calculated using Δ_{48} have considerably greater uncertainties, due to a number of factors discussed below. The Δ_{47} CEF values were 0.584 ± 0.070 (95% confidence interval) for the coral sample, 0.454 ± 0.176 for the bivalve and 0.034 ± 0.070 for the Moroccan aragonite. When the Δ_{48} values are used, the CEF values are calculated as -12.880 ± 285.396 for coral, 0.0385 ± 1.081 for the bivalve, and 0.170 ± 0.862 for the Moroccan aragonite. The derivation for calculating these uncertainties is outlined below.

The CEF value (assuming water/rock ratios close to 0) is calculated as follows.

$$\text{CEF}[\Delta_{47}] = \frac{\Delta_{47}^{\text{heated}} - \Delta_{47}^{\text{initial}}}{\Delta_{47}^{\text{equilibrium}} - \Delta_{47}^{\text{initial}}}$$

Using classical error propagation, we calculate uncertainties in the following steps.

$$(\sigma_{\text{CEF}})^2 = \left(\sigma_{\text{heated}} \frac{\partial \text{CEF}}{\partial \text{heated}} \right)^2 + \left(\sigma_{\text{initial}} \frac{\partial \text{CEF}}{\partial \text{initial}} \right)^2 + \left(\sigma_{\text{eq}} \frac{\partial \text{CEF}}{\partial \text{equilibrium}} \right)^2$$

Where σ_x corresponds to the uncertainty of a given value. The partial derivatives ($\partial_{\text{cef}}/\partial_x$) of the CEF equation with respect to heated, initial and equilibrium values are as follows

The CEF function can be generalized as follows, such that the a, b, c, and d terms change when the x term refers to the Δ_{47} value of the equilibrium, heated, and unheated values.

$$y = \frac{ax + b}{cx + d}$$

Whose derivative with respect to x is

$$y' = \frac{ad - cb}{(cx + d)^2}$$

For $\Delta_{47}^{\text{heated}}$,

$$x = \Delta_{47}^{\text{heated}}, a = 1, b = -\Delta_{47}^{\text{initial}}, c = 0, d = \Delta_{47}^{\text{equilibrium}} - \Delta_{47}^{\text{initial}}$$

so

$$\frac{\partial \text{CEF}}{\partial \text{heated}} = \frac{\Delta_{47}^{\text{equilibrium}} - \Delta_{47}^{\text{initial}}}{\left(\Delta_{47}^{\text{equilibrium}} - \Delta_{47}^{\text{initial}} \right)^2} = \frac{1}{\Delta_{47}^{\text{equilibrium}} - \Delta_{47}^{\text{initial}}}$$

For the unheated composition (initial),

$$x = \Delta_{47}^{\text{initial}}, a = -1, b = -\Delta_{47}^{\text{heated}}, c = -1, d = \Delta_{47}^{\text{equilibrium}}$$

so

$$\frac{\partial_{\text{CEF}}}{\partial_{\text{initial}}} = \frac{-\Delta_{47}^{\text{equilibrium}} - \Delta_{47}^{\text{heated}}}{\left(\Delta_{47}^{\text{equilibrium}} - \Delta_{47}^{\text{initial}}\right)^2}$$

And lastly for the equilibrium value,

$$x = \Delta_{47}^{\text{equilibrium}}, a = 0, b = \Delta_{47}^{\text{heated}} - \Delta_{47}^{\text{initial}}, c = 1, d = -\Delta_{47}^{\text{initial}}$$

so

$$\frac{\partial_{\text{CEF}}}{\partial_{\text{equilibrium}}} = \frac{-\left(\Delta_{47}^{\text{heated}} - \Delta_{47}^{\text{initial}}\right)}{\left(\Delta_{47}^{\text{equilibrium}} - \Delta_{47}^{\text{initial}}\right)^2}$$

We set each sigma value to the long-term reproducibility 95% confidence interval for the Δ values, as well as the 95% confidence interval for the Δ_{47} and Δ_{48} –Temperature relationships at 175°C (0.007‰ and 0.0132‰ respectively; from Fiebig et al., 2021).

Taking the bivalve sample as an example, we can study the relative contributions of different forms of uncertainty. The partial derivatives for CEF with respect to Δ_{heated} , Δ_{initial} and $\Delta_{\text{equilibrium}}$ for the bivalve are 4.12‰⁻¹, -13.76‰⁻¹ and 1.87‰⁻¹. These partial derivatives, when multiplied by their corresponding 95% confidence intervals for the measurements, yield 0.023, 0.077 and 0.013. From this, we conclude that analytical uncertainty for the unheated sample, is the main source of uncertainty. Thus, if future studies interested in measuring this parameter wish to best allocate replicate analyses, it is recommended that more replicates be conducted on the unheated material than the heated. Improvements can be made on the calibration error, however this is already a relatively minor contributor to uncertainty, to improve on this would require considerably more analyses of additional carbonate standards formed at known temperatures.

Text S2.

Approach for end-member mixing for isotopologues.

In systems composed of multiple phases of isotopically distinct carbonate, the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values of mixtures can be expected to represent a simple mass-balance mixing system. The abundance of any isotopologue will follow this simple linear mixing line, however the Δ_{47} and Δ_{48} values calculated from these isotopologue abundances will not. This is because the abundance of the “stochastic ratio” is calculated using the product of the relevant isotopologue ratios, and is thus a quadratic function, whereas the “true” abundance follows a linear mixing line. In the following equations, we will ignore the contributions ^{17}O isotopologues, and will instead follow the definitions recently presented by Watkins and Devriendt (2022).

The math governing the abundance of singly-substituted isotopologues is as follows.

$$^{13}R_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{[^{13}\text{C}^{16}\text{O}^{16}\text{O}]}{[^{12}\text{C}^{16}\text{O}^{16}\text{O}]} = \left(1 + \frac{\delta^{13}\text{C}}{1000}\right) ^{13}R_{\text{PDB}}^{\text{carbon}}$$

$$^{18}R_{CO_2} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{[^{12}C^{18}O^{16}O]}{[^{12}C^{16}O^{16}O]} = \left(1 + \frac{\delta^{18}O}{1000}\right) ^{18}R_{PDB}^{oxygen}$$

For mass-47 isotopologues, the following definitions are used.

$$^{47}R_{CO_2} = \frac{[^{13}C^{18}O^{16}O]}{[^{12}C^{16}O^{16}O]}$$

and

$$^{47}R_{CO_2}^{stochastic} = \frac{[^{12}C^{18}O^{16}O][^{13}C^{16}O^{16}O]}{[^{12}C^{16}O^{16}O][^{12}C^{16}O^{16}O]} = 2 * ^{13}R_{CO_2} * ^{18}R_{CO_2}$$

therefore

$$\Delta_{47} = \left(\frac{[^{13}C^{18}O^{16}O][^{12}C^{16}O^{16}O]}{[^{12}C^{18}O^{16}O][^{13}C^{16}O^{16}O]} - 1 \right) * 1000\text{‰}$$

For mass-48 isotopologues, the following definitions are used.

$$^{48}R_{CO_2} = \frac{[^{12}C^{18}O^{18}O]}{[^{12}C^{16}O^{16}O]}$$

$$^{48}R_{CO_2}^{stochastic} = \frac{[^{12}C^{18}O^{16}O][^{12}C^{18}O^{16}O]}{4[^{12}C^{16}O^{16}O][^{12}C^{16}O^{16}O]} = ^{18}R_{CO_2} * ^{18}R_{CO_2}$$

Note that the symmetry number in this case is 1, as both oxygen sites are substituted with ¹⁸O

$$\Delta_{48} = \left(\frac{4[^{12}C^{18}O^{18}O][^{12}C^{16}O^{16}O]}{[^{12}C^{18}O^{16}O][^{12}C^{18}O^{16}O]} - 1 \right) * 1000\text{‰}$$

The mixing of isotopologues, the calculated stochastic ratios and $\Delta_{47} + \Delta_{48}$ values are shown in Figure S1 as a hypothetical end-member mixing system with identical starting Δ values.

Figure S1. Modeled isotopologue mixing paths, calculated stochastic values for multiply substituted isotopologues, “true” isotopologue abundances, as well as the calculated Δ values for the mixed system. Two models are shown, one with anti-correlated $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values, and one with only changes in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$.

Data Set S1. Individual replicate analyses for all samples run in the same sessions as samples discussed in this manuscript. Anonymized samples are included, as they are necessary for error minimization.

Data Set S2. Summary table for pooled results for all clumped isotope analyses.

File S1. Matlab script and accompanying files for constructing ADD diagram.